

Legitimate Questions on “Lessons Learned From a COVID-19 Dog Screening Pilot in California K-12 Schools.”

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Dear Editor, the recent research letter¹ reported an experience on the detection of COVID-19 on children by trained dogs. My first concern is why a research that belongs to veterinary sciences is published in a paediatrics journal. Looks like the experimenters were more concerned by the dogs' wellbeing than by the children's mental health. My second concern is on the gold standard reference. There is scarce scientific proof² of the robustness, accuracy and detection performance of the antigen product, which appears to have a bias towards declaring false positives. I understand that false positives are highly desirable when enforcing draconian measures on the population. It appears that the reported research increases dramatically the bias of detection. From Table 2 in the reference, the Positive Predictive Value ($=TP/(TP+FP)$) is 18%, meaning that the 83% reported sensitivity is achieved by a massive declaration of false positives. The quality of life cost of such massive bias remains unaccounted for. Additionally, prevalence of the COVID-19 infection, according to the biased antigen test, is very low: 2.6%. This highly imbalanced sample allows for a high overall accuracy value (namely 97.3%) by the simple rule of declaring all cases negative. Hence, in such case, accuracy is a meaningless measure of detection performance. High reported specificity is also meaningless, because huge increases of false positives will not have great impact on sensitivity. F1 score ($= 2*TP / (2*TP+FP+FN)$) is a more appropriate measure of performance in imbalanced samples has a very low value, namely 0.29. A final methodological concern is the lack of comparison among dogs' detection performance. Variability among dogs should be analysed in detail, as the animals are not aseptic automatons. Conclusions relying on these weak statistical results should be very humble, however the authors seem to propose that schools should implement routine screening and maybe even maintain and own an in-house canine unit, like some new industry emerging from the COVID-19 pandemic. Finally, the discussion section is a veterinary discussion, unrelated with kids' well-being or their improved health care, so I wonder why the letter has been accepted in a leading paediatrics journal. I sincerely think that it should have been rejected on the grounds of journal scope. Readers would appreciate an explanation of why the letter was published.

1. Glaser CA, Le Marchand CE, Rizzo K, et al. Lessons Learned From a COVID-19 Dog Screening Pilot in California K-12 Schools. *JAMA Pediatr*. Published online April 24, 2023. doi:10.1001/jamapediatrics.2023.0489
2. <https://www.abbott.com/corpnewsroom/diagnostics-testing/binaxnow-performance-from-studies-in-the-field.html> accessed April 27th, 2023